

Advancing the Australian Companion Animal Registry of Cancers

ARDC AUSTRALIAN DATA PARTNERSHIPS PROJECT
FINAL REPORT

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1 PROJECT INFORMATION

INVESTMENT ID	DP713
PROJECT START AND END DATES	Jan 2021 - Dec 2023
LEAD ORGANISATION	University of Queensland
PARTNER ORGANISATIONS	QUT University of Sydney University of Adelaide Murdoch University Gribbles Veterinary Pathology IDEXX Laboratories
PROJECT CONTACT PERSON	Prof Chiara Palmieri

1.1 Background

ACARCinom is a unified, integrated and accessible national data asset comprising de-identified cancer records from major commercial and university-based veterinary pathology laboratories for identifying patterns and trends in animal cancer and quantifying the role of predisposing risk factors. Prior to ACARCinom no large-scale data were available and all the information from mostly discontinued global veterinary cancer registries failed to be realistically applicable to the Australian population of dogs and cats (e.g. breed predisposition, cancer incidence, most common types of tumour etc etc). The data repository created by ACARCinom will be critical to advance clinical and epidemiological evidence towards monitoring and evaluating the efficacy of anti-cancer treatments programs and help drive research and development of intervention priorities.

1.2 Achievement of project aims

Our core project aim was to develop the ACARCinom database as a National Data Asset with coverage for all the different cancers in the canine and feline population and for all the different Australian states. The database is integrating data from disparate sources, each with unique systems of reporting and data management, with high level of accuracy and data extraction.

Additional aims were:

1) Developing a standardised system for veterinary cancer diagnoses and coding, aligned with the human cancer classification and coding systems to allow comparative and translational studies: this was achieved in consultation with international organisations involved in providing standards for cancer nomenclature and coding (Veterinary Cancer Guidelines and Protocols – VCGP; Global Initiative for Veterinary Cancer Surveillance – GIVCS), compiling data vocabularies for cancer diagnosis (2176 terms with corresponding 953 codes), sites of the tumour (921 terms with corresponding 553 codes), certainty level of the diagnosis and grading. The automated parsing system is attributing standardised terminology to be reported into the database, taking into consideration related, obsolete terms and synonyms.

2) Creating a structured and reusable workflow for data extraction, parsing and analysis that may become a reference model for future initiatives in veterinary cancer registration. An overview of the ACARCinom workflow and import design is provided in the Figures below.

Review individual import row data

Data source: UQ v1 File source: UQ_2021_raw_data_0.1.xls Row: 61

Patient
 ID: 12785A DOB: 05/06/2011 Sex: Female Deceased:
 Canine: Breed: Post code: 4343

Case
 Ref code: 21/0155 Consultation: 04/03/2021 Age: 10

Report text (automated analysis)
 MORPHOLOGIC & FINAL DIAGNOSES:

- ★ Skin (Thorax LHS): ★ Cutaneous ★ mast cell tumour ★ low grade
- ★ Skin (RH): ★ Cutaneous ★ mast cell tumour ★ low grade
- ★ Skin (Right axilla): ★ Cutaneous ★ mast cell tumour ★ low grade

Samples found

Name	Diagnosis	Primary site	Metastasis	Grade	Certainty
Sample A	Mast cell tumour	Skin, Axilla		1/low grade	Moderate
Sample B	Mast cell tumour	Skin, Thorax			High

3) Developing a system for cancer mapping at postcode level to evaluate environmental drivers of cancer in companion animals: all the data in the ACARCinom database are anonymous and deidentified; the address of the owner/client/clinic/hospital are automatically converted into postcodes, unless provided and merged into the Australian map.

4) Creating an accessible and reusable research vocabulary for terms and codes of cancer that is paramount for any cancer registration system: the standard terminology created as per #1 has been used to generate the Vet-ICD-O Morphology vocabulary that is yet to be released through Research Vocabularies Australia. The list of concepts has been refined in consultation with the GIVCS team.

ARDC Research Vocabularies Australia ABOUT WIDGET EXPLORER GET INVOLVED+ COMMUNITY

Query or a concept

Vet-ICD-O. Morphology

Kunze-Rowan Created: 26 Aug 2022

0.4 Current

[Download](#)

Access Limited Data API
Show SPARC, BNCVM
Released 21 Nov 2022 view notes

0.3 Archived

0.2 Archived

0.1 Archived

The development of a widely accepted and comparable animal cancer registration system lends standardized animal cancer coding. The SPARC group have developed a comparative coding system for canine neoplasms—**Vet-ICD-O-canine-1**—compatible with the human ICD-O-3.2 and consistent with the currently recognized classification schemes for canine tumors. This system comprises 338 topography codes and 824 morphology codes allowing the collection of consistent epidemiologic canine cancer data and offering a robust framework for comparative oncology studies.

This example vocabulary is an HTML test version of a machine-readable encoding of morphology terms and groups.

Languages
English (United States)

Notes
Descriptive text sourced from <https://doi.org/10.33044/chem44261829>

Licence
Licence: Unknown/Other

Using browser

1 2 Filter... Sort by Label Show tooltips

Concept Concept schema Unintended collection

- 1. Vet-ICD-O-canine-1 morphology concepts (381)
- 2. Adrenal cell neoplasms (2)
- 3. Adenomas and adenocarcinomas (76)
- 4. Adnexal and skin appendage neoplasms (22)
- 5. Basal cell neoplasms (20)
- 6. Blood vessel tumors (16)
- 7. Complex epithelial neoplasms (3)
- 8. Complex mixed and stromal neoplasms (16)
- 9. Cystic, mucinous and serous neoplasms (4)
- 10. Ductal and tubular neoplasms (12)
- 11. Epithelial neoplasms, NOS (78)
- 12. Fibroepithelial neoplasms (7)
- 13. Plasmaloma neoplasms (16)
- 14. Germ cell neoplasms (10)

Use this code and/or to describe or discover resources with Vet-ICD-O. Morphology in your system

Example: Search for and select concepts in this vocabulary

[Learn more](#)

Subjects

VETERINARY SCIENCES

2 DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT OUTPUTS

2.1. Achievements against project work packages/deliverables:

DELIVERABLE / WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
1 - Data sharing agreement (agreement of all the parties involved to share data)	There has been a significant delay in finalising the data sharing agreement due to staff changes in the legal and contracts team in different institutions. However, data sharing agreements have been signed by 5 out of 6 partners, with the expectation to receive the outstanding one in December 2023.	31/12/2023
2 - Workshop with data provider and external stakeholders; presentation of the project	Instead of a workshop with the data providers, individual meetings have been organised with each of the university and private laboratories and their technical representatives. The project has been presented on social media platforms, UQ website, international conferences (annual conference of the European Society of Veterinary Pathology – September 2022, Athens; One Health symposium organised by the University of Brisbane; One Health day at the UQ School of Veterinary Science). A dedicated launch event has been organised on the 23 rd of November 2023 as part of the ARDC Community Connect program	30/11/2023
3 - Data asset and data system design (data harmonised in a single architecture with well-defined standards)	Data asset and data system design finalised; data management report available as appendix; all the aspects of data extraction, staging, transformation, visualisation and sharing completed.	31/12/2022
4 - Data access and capture from providers (automated system for data capture developed, veterinary cancer data)	The automated system for data capture has been developed. The first round of data extraction is expected to start in January 2024 with retrospective data from each data provider transferred to the central repository.	30/11/2023

transferred to the UQ central repository)		
5 - Standardisation of the data processing workflow, classification and coding Implementation of use case #1 (development of standardised veterinary cancer diagnoses)	Completed. Data dictionaries for diagnostic terms, site of the tumour, level of certainty, breed, grading finalised. Vocabulary of cancer terms and coding developed according to the standards of research Vocabulary Australia	01/02/2023
6 - Data access for users and FAIR approach implemented	Finalised. ACARCinom data access plan finalised.	31/12/2022
7 - Consultation for data quality and standards improvements. Implementation of use case #2 (Companion animals as sentinels of human cancers) and #3 (Household and environmental drivers of cancer in companion animals)	The consultation for data quality and standards improvements has been completed, even with the engagement and contribution of external parties (representatives of the Global Initiative for Veterinary Cancer Surveillance). Implementation of case #2 and #3 to be completed using the retrospective and prospective ACARCinom data. Spatial modelling analysis and evaluation of environmental factors of cancer in animals currently in progress using a small dataset of canine tumours (lymphoma, urothelial carcinoma of the urinary bladder, testicular cancer) and the results of a survey launched in December 2022.	31/12/2023
8 - Communication and dissemination, publications	A communication and engagement toolkit has been developed in consultation with ARDC. Website developed Australian Companion Animal Registry of Cancers - School of Veterinary Science - University of Queensland (uq.edu.au). After approval by the UQ marketing and engagement team, social medial platforms (facebook, Instagram, linkedin) will be created in 2024 with the support of Fassa Digital. Dissemination and publications under project outputs below.	31/12/2023

	<p>Future plans: workshop on cancer registration and coding (Brazil, May 2024), invited speaker at two workshops on cancer data and oncoepidemiology in Italy (Palermo, 28 June; Naples, 5 July), ESVP/ECVP conference (Spain, August 2024), annual conference International Association of Cancer Registry (China, October-November 2024), paper for The Scope (official newsletter of the Australian Society of Veterinary Pathology) and manuscript to be submitted to Veterinary Pathology.</p>	
<p>Impact/Outcome Monitoring Systems (Implementation Work Package)</p>		
<p>Implement data access request /registration survey for every user</p>	<p>Data management plan and data access finalised.</p>	<p>31/12/2022</p>
<p>Implement a system to collect usage tracking or other metric data embedded within the ACARCinom webpage/ database</p>	<p>ACARCinom dashboard metrics captured through Google analytics</p>	<p>30/10/2023</p>
<p>Survey generated 12 months post launch of the database for the ACARCinom mailing list users to collate feedback and inputs on the use and applicability of the database</p>	<p>ACARCinom has been launched on the 23rd of November 2023. A dedicated survey will be generated in November 2024</p>	<p>30/11/2024</p>
<p>Review of the data citation and data sharing policy of each journals in the veterinary science field or related discipline</p>	<p>The research team has collated all the information about data sharing policy of national and international journals with different quartiles and outreach to evaluate how data are cited and disseminated.</p>	<p>31/12/2022</p>
<p>Meeting with Editors-in-Chief of</p>	<p>The availability of research data and metadata has been discussed with editors-in-chief of relevant vet</p>	<p>31/03/2023</p>

<p>selected journals to implement policies for acknowledging data citations in the articles and/or reference lists and depositing data and associated metadata at the time of article submission or integrated with article submission</p>	<p>science journals (Veterinary Pathology, Research in Veterinary Science and Veterinary and Animal science) and guidelines/policies are already in place at the time of article submission.</p>	
<p>A proposal for implementing new policies and systems for data and software citations will be submitted to the relevant parties, followed by a meeting to discuss strategies for introducing research data policies</p>	<p>A meeting has been organised with representatives from other veterinary cancer registries (Nilov, Vet-Onconet) to discuss the issues of data and software citations. While this has been resolved at journal level (see above), no policies or guidelines are in place in other dissemination avenues (e.g. conferences, workshops). A dedicated meeting will be organised in 2024 with other parties managing veterinary data (e.g., VetCompass, Take CHARGE).</p>	<p>Continuing</p>

2.2. Project outputs

ACARCinom database: the first public version of the Australian Companion Animal registry of Cancers has been released in November 2023 with testing data collated from each data provider. A new intake of data is expected in January 2024 with a 3-6 months plan of prospective data transfer from 2024 onwards.

Conference presentations: we will be actively promoting the use of ACARCinom through research outputs (conferences, publications) from our research team from 2024 onwards. Meanwhile, ACARCinom has already been mentioned and presented in international conferences:

1. Palmieri C. Cancer registration in companion animals: towards a global approach with the Global Initiative for Veterinary Cancer Surveillance (keynote lecture) – Annual ESVP/ECVP congress 2022, September 7-10, Athens (Greece)

2. Palmieri C. Environment and cancer: how cancer data in companion animals can help. (invited speaker). Workshop on cancer data in companion animals to improve pet and human health, University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences – UVAS Lahore, 05 December 2022.
3. Palmieri C. Coding of tumours of the genital and urinary tract, respiratory system and endocrine system (Invited speaker). GIVS international workshop on tumour coding, 26 May and 02 June 2022.
4. Palmieri C. Veterinary cancer registries (invited speaker). 4th International Conference on One Health, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine Universitas Brawijaya (Indonesia), 26-27 October 2021
5. Palmieri C. Cancer registration and Coding: the only tools for an effective comparative oncoepidemiology. Italy, 10 June 2023

2.3. Outreach and training activities

ACTIVITY	ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION	NO. OF PARTICIPANTS	DATE OF ACTIVITY
Conference presentations	All the conference/workshop presentations as outlined in section 2.2	We have not documented the number of people who attended each event	Please refer to the dates as listed in section 2.2.
ACARCinom launch event	Presentation of the project	30 in person and 18-20 online	23/11/2023
Video	3 minutes video summarising the structure of the database and how to navigate the dashboard	N/A	November 2023 (video accessible through the ACARCinom website)
Educational material	Two power point presentations on cancer registration and coding (please refer to the ARDC community connect program final report for further details)	N/A	November-December 2023 (video accessible through the ACARCinom website)

3 SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

While developing the ACARCinom platform, we have considered the post-project continuity and sustainability of the platform as major goals moving forward, especially considering previous attempts in developing long-lived cancer registries in companion animals. The platform has been designed in a way that it requires minimal maintenance with the data sources already in place. The software engineer team and the research team have been actively working in making sure that the ACARCinom parser is able to recognise even minimal changes in the raw data. However, there are ample opportunities for expansion, in terms of diversified data sources and applicability of data. We believe that ACARCinom will become a central platform for all cancer researchers and HDR students to fulfil their research goals and to attract Category 1-3 funding and thus maintain a long-term sustainable growth of the platform. Therefore, the long-term operating costs will be securely covered by diversified and sustainable funding sources, both nationally and internationally, especially looking at application of cancer data in comparative oncology and environmental health.

4 FAIR

FAIR Data Actions

#	FAIR ACTION	DETAILS OF IMPLEMENTATION
1	All data outputs are assigned appropriate PIDs, preferably a DOI	DOI: 10.48610/6b7fccf
2	All data outputs have metadata to enable discovery	Metadata are available in the UQ eSpace repository and in Research data Australia
3	All data outputs have a record in Research Data Australia	See: https://researchdata.edu.au/acarcinomaustralian-companion-animal-registry-cancer/2205822
4	All data outputs are registered with relevant discipline-specific discovery aggregators (Recommended , if they exist)	N/A

5	The persistent identifier for the data output being described is included in the metadata	The DOI for the dataset is available in the metadata in UQ eSpace repository and in Research Data Australia
6	All data outputs are made as openly available as possible; they are only closed where necessary	Access is mediated to the non-aggregated data available on the ACARcinom website as per data access proposal acarcinom.org.au
7	All data outputs are made available through a repository	The data can be accessed through the ACARcinom dashboard acarcinom.org.au
8	All data outputs are available as a download and/or accessible through an open, documented API (where data is not closed)	API is not available because only highly aggregated data are provided through the dashboard
9	If the data outputs are not openly available, there is a clear description on the landing page on how to request access to the data outputs and the conditions that need to be met	Information will be available on the ACARcinom website from early 2024 on how to request access to the data
10	The persistent identifier for the data output points to a landing page about the data output, even if the data output is not public (open).	DOI (https://doi.org/10.48610/6b7fccf) linked to a landing page on the UQ eSpace repository.
11	If the data output is not openly available there is an authorisation and authentication procedure to provide access to the data	Each data provider (provisional authorised users) has access to the non-aggregated data through a login on the ACARcinom dashboard. An admin account has been provided to the project leader and co-leader for managing the ETS process.
12	The persistent identifier for the data output continues to point to a landing page, even if the data output is no longer available, and there is a policy to maintain these landing pages	The data are released through a UQ website linked to the dashboard and the landing page will be hosted on the two servers for unlimited time
13	Data outputs use community-agreed standard data formats (where such agreed formats exist)	Standards have been finalised and are aligned to international standards for terminology, classification and coding

14	Metadata for the data output uses community-agreed standards (where such agreed standards exist)	Standards have been finalised and are aligned to international standards for terminology, classification and coding
15	Data and metadata use community-agreed vocabularies, data models and ontologies (Recommended , preferably internationally agreed ones where they exist)	Standards have been finalised and are aligned to international standards for terminology, classification and coding
16	Metadata contains persistent identifiers for research objects and entities (people, organisations) linked to the data outputs (including ORCIDs, grantIDs, RAIDs, DOIs, IGSNs)	The ACARCinom webpage contains links to the ORCIDs of the project leader and co-leader and the ARDC GrantID Australian Companion Animal Registry of Cancers - School of Veterinary Science - University of Queensland (uq.edu.au)
17	All data outputs are assigned a machine readable licence (preferably CC-BY 4.0)	Aggregated data is made available through a CC BY-NC SA4.0 or CC BY-NC 4.0 licence
18	The licence information is available in a machine readable form on the landing page that the persistent identifier (for the data output) refers to	The licence is indicated on the UQ eSpace page ACARCinom_Australian Companion Animal Registry of Cancer - UQ eSpace
19	There is a citation statement for the data output on the landing page that the persistent identifier refers to	Citation statement available on ACARCinom_Australian Companion Animal Registry of Cancer (researchdata.edu.au)
20	Provenance information on the data output is attached alongside the data (Recommended)	The ACARCinom website includes a link to the dashboard with all the aggregated data with all the information about sources of data
21	Relevant discipline-specific metadata to enable reuse is captured and presented alongside the data output following research community best practice (Recommended)	N/A

5 PROJECT IMPACT

The ARDC and the Government wish to demonstrate the impact on researchers, industry and the general public of the NCRIS investment. Please complete the following sections as relevant to your program.

5.1 Communications and Engagement

Please refer to 2.2 and 2.3 for outreach activities

5.2 Research Outcomes Planning

ACTIVITY	DETAILS
Establishment of a monitoring framework (for project outcomes and impacts)	Creation of the ACARCinom data asset with establishment of a well structured partnership and consolidated operational framework; ACARCinom metrics regularly tracked using Google analytics.
	Research manuscript – number of peer-reviewed articles in high-impact journals: this outcome required the establishment of the ACARCinom data asset. Two manuscripts planned for 2024. Citation analysis will be performed at 6-months and 1-year after publication.
	Research training: DVCLinSC students (combined clinical residency in veterinary pathology and research program) have been trained on cancer data and coding since the beginning of the project; one HDR student is applying for a competitive UQ scholarship in 2024. Implementation of a system to track the number of HDR students involved in the projects and the number of FTE working on the project with a particular focus on gender balance and diversity.
	Research outreach: the ACARCinom communication strategies plan includes a series of initiatives for a broad outreach and wide dissemination of the research outputs. This will be implemented on the ACARCinom website and

	social media platforms. Community engagement activities are also included in the Community connect program plan.
	<p>Research project grants:</p> <p>1) Advancing comparative oncoepidemiology of environmental cancers for improved surveillance and prevention in Australia – IMPACT philanthropy program (\$47,393)</p> <p>2) Comparative oncology and environment (survey) – UQ strategic funds (\$12,000)</p> <p>The monitoring framework includes the evaluation of the total number of spin off projects and collaborations 1- and 2 year post project.</p>
Inputs from research users in design of the infrastructure	Experts and research users approached for the design of the infrastructure: GIVCS, Vet_onconet, Italian association of veterinary cancer registries, QLD cancer registry. Residents and junior pathologists at the UQ School of Veterinary Science have been engaged to trial the use and application of the database (UQ data only), testing the accessibility of the information provided through the ACARCinom repository
Partnerships with research translation specialists	The technical advisory group has been consulted in the first stage of the project – definition of the data system requirements. Other partners (new data providers, specialists, clinicians) will be approached once the final ACARCinom database is made available to the community
Establishment of policies, systems and workflows to track uptake (of project outcomes)	Impact indicators as above are included within the ACARCinom KPIs and they will be used to monitor activities and reported annually, even in the post project continuity stage. Impact indicators are derived from the OECD’s reference framework for assessing the scientific and socio-economic impact of research infrastructures.

6 LESSONS LEARNED

6.1 What Went Well?

The main goal of this project was to deliver a data asset capable of capturing the most comprehensive and reliable cancer data in Australian companion animals. In reality, aside from this main broad purpose, the technical skills and diverse knowledge gained through the project were actually equally important and shareable within the ACARCI^{nom} research team and broadly within the research community.

Within the research team, reflecting on the data extraction process from each provider turned out to be a tremendous experience for improving and implementing the original database features – all information that can be shared across the veterinary pathology lab community for a more effective and accurate collation of data. Since just a few initiatives in veterinary cancer registration are currently in place, developing an efficient framework and design for data extraction/transformation/analysis is becoming a reference tool to be reused by other groups willing to build such a capability in their country or institution. The vocabulary created through ACARCI^{nom} has been already shared with other international research groups aiming to develop systems for cancer data capture.

6.2 What Could be Improved?

Overall, we are very satisfied with the final outcome of the project, both in terms of the main project delivery (ACARCI^{nom} dashboard) and the establishment of a collegial partnership within the research team.

One of the most unexpectedly complicated components of the project has been the finalisation of the data sharing agreement. That was the only major issue delaying the launch of the database. Moving from a multi-institutional agreement to split agreement with individual institutions has been beneficial to accelerate the process. However, we may need to strategically think about implementing the approval process for short-term projects or moving towards the creation of an overarching nation-wide agreement for data sharing in animal health.